

JOB SATISFACTION OF TEACHING AND NON-TEACHING PERSONNEL OF AKLAN STATE UNIVERSITY: A CASE IN POINT

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive correlation study was conducted to have an in-depth analysis of the level of job satisfaction among teaching and non-teaching personnel of Aklan State University, Main Campus for the school year 2013-2014. The indicators used for job satisfaction were; feedback, teamwork, quality and customer focus, mission and purpose, compensation, work place and resources, communication, opportunities for growth, work/life balance and work pace and fairness.

A total of 147 personnel respondents participated in this study. The level of job satisfaction was assessed by the teaching and non-teaching personnel. Frequency, percentage and mean were used to analyze the data.

Indicators such as, feedback, teamwork, quality and customer focus, compensation, workplace and resources, communication, work/life balance and work pace, fairness, respect for management, respect for employees, performance and accountability and personal expression/diversity all were rated by the respondents as dissatisfied.

It was noted that mission and purpose were rated by the teaching and non-teaching personnel as satisfied. The difference between the level of job satisfaction among teaching and non-teaching personnel differ significantly. The results further revealed that the teaching personnel were more dissatisfied compared to the non-teaching personnel.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, teaching, non-teaching personnel, dissatisfied*

Feedback. The teaching (2.35) and non-teaching (2.46) have dissatisfied level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.39) in terms of receiving feedback.

Teamwork. The teaching personnel have dissatisfied (2.38) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.67) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.47) in terms of teamwork.

Quality and Customer Focus. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.42) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.92) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.58) in terms of quality and customer focus.

Mission and Purpose. The teaching personnel have Satisfied (4.12) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.11) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are Satisfied (3.79) in terms of mission and purpose.

Compensation. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.37) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.81) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.51) in terms of compensation.

Table 1. Level of Job Satisfaction Among Teaching and Non-teaching Personnel of Aklan State University

Indicators	Personnel					
	Teaching		Non-Teaching		Total	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Feedback	2.35	Dissatisfied	2.46	Dissatisfied	2.39	Dissatisfied
Teamwork	2.38	Dissatisfied	2.65	Uncertain	2.47	Dissatisfied
Quality and Customer Focus	2.42	Dissatisfied	2.92	Uncertain	2.58	Uncertain
Mission and Purpose	4.12	Satisfied	3.11	Uncertain	3.79	Satisfied
Compensation	2.37	Dissatisfied	2.81	Uncertain	2.51	Uncertain
Workplace and Resources	2.42	Dissatisfied	3.20	Uncertain	2.67	Uncertain
Communication	2.16	Dissatisfied	2.98	Uncertain	2.42	Dissatisfied
Opportunities for Growth	2.03	Dissatisfied	2.82	Uncertain	2.28	Dissatisfied
Work/Life Balance and Work Pace	2.18	Dissatisfied	3.09	Uncertain	2.47	Dissatisfied
Fairness	1.96	Dissatisfied	3.00	Uncertain	2.30	Dissatisfied
Respect for Management	2.07	Dissatisfied	2.94	Uncertain	2.35	Dissatisfied
Respect for Employees	2.19	Dissatisfied	3.49	Uncertain	2.61	Uncertain
Performance and Accountability	2.42	Dissatisfied	3.04	Uncertain	2.62	Uncertain
Personal Expression/Diversity	2.08	Dissatisfied	2.97	Uncertain	2.37	Dissatisfied
As Entire Group	2.37	Dissatisfied	3.00	Uncertain	2.57	Uncertain

Workplace and Resources. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.42) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.20) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.67) in terms of compensation.

Communication. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.16) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.98) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.42) in terms of communication.

Opportunities for Growth. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.03) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.82) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.28) in terms of opportunities for growth.

Work/Life Balance and Work Pace. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.18) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.09) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.47) in terms of work/life balance and work pace.

Fairness. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (1.96) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.00) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.30) in terms of fairness.

Respect for Management. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.07) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.94) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.35) in terms of respect for management.

Respect for Employees. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.19) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.49) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.61) in terms of respect for employees.

Performance and Accountability. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.42) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.04) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.62) in terms of performance and accountability.

Personal Expression/Diversity. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.08) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (2.97) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are dissatisfied (2.37) in terms of personal expression/diversity.

As Entire Group. The teaching personnel have Dissatisfied (2.37) level of job satisfaction while the non-teaching personnel have Uncertain (3.00) level of job satisfaction. The personnel of ASU are uncertain (2.57) on their job satisfaction as an entire group.

Job Satisfaction

Indicators such as, feedback, teamwork, quality and customer focus, compensation, workplace and resources, communication, work/life balance and work pace, fairness, respect for management, respect for employees, performance and accountability and personal expression/diversity all were rated by the respondents as dissatisfied.

It was noted that mission and purpose were rated by the teaching and non-teaching personnel as satisfied.

Difference between the job satisfaction of the teaching and non-teaching personnel

Results revealed that the level of job satisfaction of teaching and non-teaching personnel differ significantly. The results further revealed that the teaching personnel were more dissatisfied compare to the non-teaching personnel.

Conclusions

Both teaching and non-teaching personnel were dissatisfied with their present job.

Recommendations

On the basis of the conclusions forwarded, it is recommended that the university must create policies on reward, recognition and on the spot promotion systems for deserving personnel this will surely strengthen work ethics and morale of ASU personnel.